

THE PHONOLOGY OF A GYARONG DIALECT

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The Gyarong dialect whose phonological system I describe here is that spoken in Tzuta, a village formerly in the Lifan district of Szechuan (it is now in the district of Li in the Szechuan Autonomous Region for the Tibetans). I collected the material cited in 1943, while working in a research project headed by Professor Fang-kuei Li at Yenching University (Ch'engtu).

This dialect has twelve stops (k, kh, g, t̚, t̚h, d̚, t̚, th, d̚, p, ph, b), ten fricatives (h, ʃ, ʒ, s, z, r, s, z, l, l), four nasals (ɲ, ɲ̃, n, m), two semivowels (j, w), and five vowels (i, e, a, o, u). I cannot say whether tones are phonemic. When confronted with what seemed to be homonyms, my informant made distinctions on the basis of tone, e. g. tem̃ña 'eye' with high level tones on both syllables, tem̃ña 'steamed bread' with mid level tones on both syllables, and termi 'man' with high level tones on both syllables, termi 'a name', with high tone on the first syllable and high falling tone on the second. In connected texts, however, the tones vary, and I have been unable to correlate this variation with anything in the surrounding environment.

1. The stops, classified by point of articulation, are:

velar	domal	dental	labial
<u>k</u>	<u>t̚</u>	<u>t̚</u>	<u>p</u>
<u>kh</u>	<u>t̚h</u>	<u>th</u>	<u>ph</u>
<u>g</u>	<u>d̚</u>	<u>d̚</u>	<u>b</u>

Clusters of stop followed by fricative are:

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velar		palatal	domal	dental	labial
<u>kr</u>		<u>tš</u>	<u>tʂ</u>	<u>ts</u>	<u>pr</u>
<u>kh</u> <u>r</u>	<u>kh</u> <u>l</u>	<u>tš</u> <u>h</u>	<u>tʂ</u> <u>h</u>	<u>tsh</u>	<u>ph</u> <u>r</u>
<u>gr</u>	<u>gl</u>	<u>dž</u>	<u>dʒ</u>	<u>dz</u>	<u>br</u>

These consonants and consonant clusters appear both initially and intervocalically, with the exception of khl, which occurs only before j (cf. below, §5). Unreleased k, t, and p also occur finally in random occurrences of some forms; in other occurrences they are absent. (For examples, see the Appendix to this article.)

2. Fricatives, single and in clusters, are:

velar	palatal	domal	dental
<u>h</u>	<u>š</u>	<u>ʂ</u>	<u>s</u> <u>ʃ</u>
	<u>ž</u>	<u>z</u> <u>r</u>	<u>z</u> <u>l</u>
		<u>ʂ</u> <u>l</u> <u>r</u> <u>l</u>	<u>sl</u>

Semivowels are:

palatal	labial
<u>j</u>	<u>w</u>

The fricatives and w appear initially and intervocalically; s and r also appear finally. j only occurs after other consonants.

3. The nasals are:

velar	palatal	dental	labial
<u>ŋ</u>	<u>ɲ</u>	<u>n</u>	<u>m</u>

ŋ, n, and m appear initially, intervocalically, and finally; ɲ appears only initially and intervocalically.

4. Certain velars and palatals, and s and r, occur in clusters in -w: kw, khw, (gw) ɣw, tšhw, sw, and rw.

5. A number of consonants and consonant clusters may be followed by j,

as indicated below (note that members of the palatal series are not found in this number). wj is phonetically [ü].

Sequences in parentheses occur only in larger consonant sequences; gwj, for example, occurs only after z.

	velars	domal	dental	labial
	<u>kj</u>		<u>tj</u>	<u>pj</u>
	<u>kwj</u>			
	<u>khj</u>	<u>thj</u>	<u>thj</u>	<u>phj</u>
	<u>khwj</u>			
	<u>gj</u>	<u>dj</u>	<u>dj</u>	<u>bj</u>
	(<u>gwj</u>)			
	(<u>krj</u>)	<u>tʃj</u>	<u>tsj</u>	<u>prj</u>
	<u>khrij</u>	<u>tʃhij</u>	<u>tshj</u>	(<u>phrj</u>)
	<u>grj</u>			(<u>brj</u>)
	<u>khlj</u>			
		<u>sj</u>	<u>sj</u>	
			<u>swj</u>	
		<u>zj</u>	<u>zj</u>	
			<u>lj</u>	
		<u>rj</u>	<u>lj</u>	
		<u>rwj</u>		
		<u>slj</u>	<u>slj</u>	
		<u>rlj</u>		
	<u>ɖj</u>		<u>nj</u>	<u>mj</u>
	<u>ɖwj</u>			
	<u>wj</u>			

6. The above consonants and consonant clusters, with the exception of sl,

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ʃl, and rl, can be preceded by s/z, ʃ/z, r, k/g, p/b, m, n, and ɟ, as indicated in the chart below. Some of the resulting clusters occur both initially and intervocalically; some, e.g. skhj, occur only intervocalically. The distribution of s/z, ʃ/z, k/g, and p/b correlates with the voiceless/voiced quality of the following consonant. Before nasals, however, only s, ʃ, r, m, n, and ɟ occur.

	<u>s/z</u>	<u>ʃ/z</u>	<u>r</u>	<u>k/g</u>	<u>p/b</u>	<u>m</u>	<u>n</u>	<u>ɟ</u>
velars	X	X	X		X	X		X
palatals	X*		X	X		X	X	X
domals		X	X	X	X	X	X	X
dental stops and <u>n</u>	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
dental affricates and fricatives			X	X	X	X	X	X
labials	X	X	X	X		X	X	X

* The palatal, ɲ, is preceded by ʃ, not s.

(a) The velar series may be preceded by s/z, ʃ/z, r, p/b, m, and ɟ, as follows:

<u>sk</u>	<u>ʃk</u>	<u>rk</u>	<u>pk</u>	<u>mk</u>	<u>ɟk</u>
	<u>ʃkr</u>			<u>mkr</u>	
	<u>ʃkrj</u>				
<u>skw</u>	<u>ʃkw</u>				
<u>skj</u>		<u>rkj</u>	<u>pkj</u>		
<u>skh</u>	<u>ʃkh</u>	<u>rkh</u>		<u>mkh</u>	<u>ɟkh</u>
	<u>ʃkhr</u>		<u>pkhr</u>	<u>mkhr</u>	<u>ɟkhr</u>
	<u>ʃkhw</u>	<u>rkhw</u>			
<u>skhj</u>					
<u>zg</u>	<u>ʒg</u>	<u>rg</u>		<u>mg</u>	<u>ɟg</u>
	<u>ʒgr</u>				<u>ɟgr</u>
	<u>ʒgrj</u>				

zgwj

ɣgwj

rgj

sɣ

ʂɣ

rɣ

mɣ

rɣj

(b) The palatal series may be preceded by s/z (ʂ before ɲ), r, k/g, m, n, and ɣ:

stš

rtš

ktš

rtšw

ntšw

rtšh

ktšh

rtšhw

zdž

rdž

mdž

ndž

ɣdž

kš

mš

rž

nž

sɲ

rɲ

mɲ

nɲ

ɣɲ

(c) The domal series may be preceded by ʂ/z, r, k/g, p/b, m, n, and ɣ:

st

kt

pt

stj

nd

sts

rts

kts

pts

mts

nts

ɣts

ktšj

ntšj

stsh

rtsh

ktsh

mtsh

ntsh

ntšhj

bdz

mdz

ndz

rš

kš

mš

nš

ɣš

rz

gz

ɣz

ɣr

(d) The dental stops and nasal may be preceded by s/z, ʂ/z, r, k/g, p/b,

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m, n, and ŋ:

<u>st</u>	<u>ʂt</u>	<u>rt</u>	<u>kt</u>	<u>pt</u>	<u>mt</u>	<u>nt</u>
<u>stj</u>	<u>ʂtj</u>	<u>rtj</u>		<u>ptj</u>	<u>mtj</u>	<u>ntj</u>
<u>sth</u>	<u>ʂth</u>	<u>rth</u>		<u>pth</u>	<u>mth</u>	<u>nth</u>
<u>zd</u>	<u>ʂd</u>	<u>rd</u>	<u>gd</u>		<u>md</u>	<u>nd</u>
	<u>z dj</u>	<u>rdj</u>			<u>mdj</u>	<u>ŋdj</u>
<u>sn</u>	<u>ʂn</u>	<u>rn</u>				
<u>snj</u>	<u>ʂnj</u>	<u>rnj</u>			<u>mnj</u>	<u>ŋnj</u>
						<u>ŋl</u>
						<u>nlj</u>

(e) Dental affricates and fricatives may be preceded by r, k, p/b, m, n, and

ŋ:

<u>rts</u>	<u>kts</u>	<u>pts</u>	<u>mts</u>	<u>nts</u>	<u>ŋts</u>
<u>rtsj</u>	<u>ktsj</u>	<u>ptsj</u>			
<u>rtsh</u>		<u>ptsh</u>	<u>mtsh</u>	<u>ntsh</u>	
		<u>ptshj</u>		<u>ntshj</u>	
		<u>bdz</u>	<u>mdz</u>	<u>ndz</u>	
<u>rs</u>	<u>ks</u>	<u>ps</u>	<u>ms</u>		<u>ŋs</u>
<u>rsj</u>			<u>msj</u>		
<u>rz</u>					<u>ŋz</u>
	<u>gzj</u>				

(f) The labial series may be preceded by s/z, ʂ/z, r, k/g, m, n, and ŋ:

<u>sp</u>	<u>ʂp</u>	<u>rp</u>	<u>kp</u>	<u>mp</u>	<u>ŋp</u>
	<u>spr</u>		<u>kpr</u>		
			<u>kprj</u>		
<u>spj</u>	<u>ʂpj</u>	<u>rpi</u>	<u>kpj</u>		<u>ŋpj</u>
		<u>rph</u>	<u>kph</u>	<u>mph</u>	<u>ŋph</u>

				<u>mphrj</u>		
				<u>mphj</u>		
<u>zb</u>	<u>z̥b</u>	<u>rb</u>		<u>mb</u>	<u>nb</u>	<u>ɣb</u>
	<u>z̥br</u>			<u>mbr</u>		
				<u>mbrj</u>		
	<u>z̥bj</u>			<u>mbj</u>	<u>nbj</u>	
<u>sm</u>	<u>s̥m</u>	<u>rm</u>				<u>ɣm</u>
		<u>rmj</u>				<u>ɣmj</u>

7. The vowels (i, e, a, o, u) all occur in noninitial position; except for o, they also occur initially, e.g. iɖeɣ 'I peel, husk'; eʒo 'he, she, it', ete 'that one', eptshi 'its outside'; atshu 'son-in-law', urje 'wage'.

Phonetically, i is [i], a [a], u [u], and o [ɔ]. e is [ə]~[e]. Two conditions determine the appearance of the second allophone: e is (1) preceded by a palatal or a consonant cluster in -j; and (2) not followed by -k or -ɣ.

Sandhi-produced diphthongs result when i or u are immediately preceded by the vowel of a prefix, e.g. iɖeɣ 'I peel', naideɣ 'I have peeled'; urje 'wage', teurje 'ones' wage'.

There are restrictions on the occurrence of these vowels: (1) a does not occur after -w̥j-; and (2) o and u do not occur after consonant clusters which have -w̥-, -j-, or -w̥j- as their last member. Exception: khekhjui (n.pr. of a place).

The finals are:

<u>-i</u>	<u>-iu</u>	<u>-is</u>	<u>-ir</u>	<u>-ip</u>	<u>-im</u>	<u>-it</u>	<u>-in</u>	<u>-ik</u>	<u>-ij</u>
<u>-e</u>	<u>-ei</u>	<u>-eu</u>	<u>-es</u>	<u>-er</u>	<u>-ep</u>	<u>-em</u>	<u>-et</u>	<u>-en</u>	<u>-ek</u> <u>-ej</u>
<u>-a</u>	<u>-ai</u>	<u>-au</u>	<u>-as</u>	<u>-ar</u>	<u>-ap</u>	<u>-am</u>	<u>-at</u>	<u>-an</u>	<u>-ak</u> <u>-aj</u>
<u>-o</u>	<u>-oi</u>		<u>-or</u>		<u>-om</u>	<u>-ot</u>	<u>-on</u>	<u>-ok</u>	<u>-oj</u>
<u>-u</u>	<u>-ui</u>	<u>-us</u>	<u>-ur</u>	<u>-up</u>	<u>-um</u>	<u>-ut</u>	<u>-un</u>		<u>-uj</u>

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There are also instances of final consonant clusters: koms 'on top of a door', šenkhans 'on top of a šenkhan (where images of gods are kept)'.
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APPENDIX

The examples below are grouped under numbers corresponding to those of the relevant sections in the article.

1. (For examples of final consonants, see 7.)

Velars:

k-: kam 'the colter of a plough', kom 'door'; -k-: taku 'head', meki 'underneath'

kh-: khi 'dog', khui 'bowl', khey 'tiger'; -kh-: kekhui 'foolish'

g-: gokar 'a kind of woolen fabric', genbje 'a temple'; -g-: dagui 'the district of Kuàn in Szech'uan'

kr-: kres 'conference'; -kr-: žiukri 'vegetable oil'

khr-: khrəp 'I beat'; -khr-: tekhru 'elbow'

gr-: greq 'I scrape'; -gr-: pragrom 'a chicken egg'

-gl-: teгла 'shuttle'

Palatals:

tš-: tši 'wheat', tše 'a river deer', tšu 'stone'; -tš-: etšer 'its root', tatšim 'fertilizer', ketši 'large'

tšh-: tšhe 'wine', tšhu 'village'; -tšh-: tatšhu 'wedge', khretšho 'pepper tree'

dž-: džu 'bamboo', dži 'south'; -dž-: tadžu 'lock'

Domals:

ɬ-: ɬam 'I sew', ɬep 'I spread'; -ɬ-: teɬe, n.pr. of a place, keɬo 'six', waɬam 'his fat'

ɬh-: ɬhezek 'resin'; -ɬh-: ɬethu 'light'

ɖ-: ɖenbu 'going out', ɖali 'earthquake'; -ɖ-: neɖəp 'I walk', teɖe 'skin'

ɬs-: ɬsam 'house', ɬsei 'here', ɬsoktsi, n.pr. of a place; -ɬs-: teɬse 'water', taɬse

song', keṭṣar 'narrow'

ṭṣh-: ṭṣhom 'a water bucket carried on one's back', ṭṣhing 'I go', ṭṣham 'a lama's dance'; -ṭṣh-: keṭṣhi 'sweet', keṭṣnim 'thin (in diameter)'

ḍz-: ḍzero 'cicada', ḍzeru 'louse eggs'; -ḍz-: kawadze 'to chew'

Dentals:

t-: tam 'I beat', taṅ 'I boil (water)'; -t-: metaṅ 'I see', krata, n.pr. of a place, ketu 'a wildcat'

th-: thi 'what?', thatho 'a pine tree', tharna 'a steelyard for money'; -th-: tathu 'woolen fabrics'

d-: dut, n.pr. of a cruel man (in legends), do 'east', dedu 'a wild pigeon'; -d-: tado 'poison'

ts-: tsoro 'socks' tsurer 'star', tsetje, n.pr. of a place; -ts-: etsi 'his life', ketsu 'monkey'

tsh-: tshapje 'malaria', tsharei 'natron'; -tsh-: tatshiu 'sneezing', atshu 'son-in-law'

dz-: dzaži 'flea'; -dz-: medzu 'at ones will'

Labials:

p-: pas 'a wild animal similar to a pig', pežiu 'rat', papei 'silver', peṅ 'I come'; -p-: tepo 'red hemp', tapat 'flower', lapu 'mule'

ph-: phat 'to pick, pluck; climb over', phatak 'dumplings made of corn flour', phaṅ 'I divide'; -ph-: taphi 'guest', epha 'half', taphan 'bosom'

b-: baro 'horse', bertsje 'knife', beṅ 'I carry on my back'; -b-: babuṅ 'a kind of insect', zebar 'wooden partition', tabem 'a pair'

pr-: prak 'rok', prakhu 'owl', preṅ 'I tear'; -pr-: taprer 'supper', keprom 'white'

phr-: phruṅ 'I blow', phramu 'rosary'; -phr-: tephrer 'grandson'

br-: breṅ 'rhinoceros', brastak 'a kind of bee'; -br-: žabra, n.pr. of a place

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2.

h-: hanoi 'below', harnak 'a kind of bird'; -h-: tahur 'once', taham 'yawning'

š-: šaj 'I send (a gift to someone)'

ž-: žalu 'a large calabash', žantan 'knowledge, learning'; -ž-: težiu 'ghost', težim 'a bear', kežo 'a goat'

š-: ši 'firewood', šerša 'fence', šaru 'bone'; -š-: taši 'a wealthy man', kešek 'new'

z-: zuḡ 'I accuse (someone)', zardžin, n.pr. of a place, zaḡdin 'puttees'; -z-: tezu 'chopsticks', ṭšhezar 'swimming', wazi 'his sister'

šl-: šlaḡ 'I release'; -šl-: ašlu 'yesterday'

r-: ruḡ 'I look'; -r-: teru 'horn', khara 'ant', phoraḡ 'Peking'

rl-: rlaḡ 'I have no heir'; -rl-: berlen 'a carpenter's plane', terler 'yak'

s-: sar 'louse', sanan 'good luck', sarža 'fan'; -s-: kesu 'sheep', kesom 'three'

z-: zai 'ladder', zan 'I eat', zarka 'a medicinal herb'; -z-: tazar 'milling (flour)', tazom 'bridge'

sl-: slam 'I roll up', slapen 'teacher'; -sl-: keslat 'exhausted'

l-: laškar 'a head ornament made of coral', lašje 'Lhasa'; -l-: ṭšhałam 'leather boots'

l-: luḡḡje 'place; valley', laḡje 'lama', lenbu 'tribal chief'; -l-: khali 'wind', telu 'milk'

w-: waržet 'aight', wamtsher 'lying on one's side'; -w-: tawu 'ceremonies performed on the anniversary of a death', grawu, n.pr. of a place

3.

ḡ-: ḡa 'I'; -ḡ-: paḡei 'silver', taḡei 'sun'

ň-: ňi 'you (plural)', ňiḡ 'I sit down', ňakprje 'meat dumpling'; -ň-: meňu 'a tapered basket carried on one's back', meňaḡ 'cat'

n-: nu 'you', noḡ 'I drive (cattle)', namšek 'soul'; -n-: tanai 'morning', kenak 'black'

m-: mezi 'gunpowder', mesnom 'girl'; -m-: temu 'sky', tami 'foot'

4.

kw-: kwa 'spade'; -kw-: sakwan 'I uproot'

khw-: khwaštšan 'silk; satin'

ɣw-: ɣwa 'to be'; -ɣw-: kaɣwu 'butter lamp'

tšhw-: tšhwan 'I return'; -tšhw-: tšhetšhwa 'blister'

sw-: swai 'barley'

rw-: rwaɣ 'I get up'; -rw-: terwu 'buckwheat', tarwa 'hunting and fishing'

5.

Velars and w:

kj-: kjar 'a steelyard used e.g. for weighing meat or vegetables'; -kj-: tekjar 'sinews', tekjep 'needle'

kwj-: kwje 'kitchen'

-khj-: khekhjui, n.pr. of a place, tekhje 'mouth'

khwj-: khwje 'bedroom'

gj-: gjaɣ 'I shout'; -gj-: zegje 'saddle'

khrij-: khrijetšho 'pepper tree'; -khrij-: kestšalakhrje 'of variegated colors'

-grj-: wegrje 'the lower level'

-khlj-: tekhlje 'the upper arm'

ɣj-: ɣjaɣ 'I have intercourse with someone', ɣjesu, n.pr. of a place

-ɣwj-: ňiɣwje 'cow'

wj-: wjan 'I wear'; -wj-: šawje 'a wild deer', kewje 'thin', tewjet 'clothes'

Domals:

thj-: thjewu 'pen, stable'

-dj-: žedje, 'name of a tree'

tšj-: tšjerje, n.pr. of a place; -tšj-: ɣatšjep 'bitter', ketšje 'poor'

-tšhj-: šatšhje 'world'

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ʃj-: ʃje 'meat; flesh'; -ʃj-: ʃtauʃje 'a kind of mushroom'

zj-: zje 'to fall'

rj-: rje 'to want'

-rwj-: tarwjet 'get up!' parwje 'a vessel used in religious ceremonies'

-ʃlj-: (ka)waʃlje 'slippery'

-rlj-: arlje 'bean curd'

Dentals:

tj-: tjaḡ 'I boil (water)', tjaḡden 'a small copper bowl for pure water (for religious purposes)'; -tj-: tatjar 'stick', teʃatjak 'belly; stomach'

-thj-: tethje 'book'

-dj-: medja 'he arrives'

-tsj-: petsjar 'warm season', ketsje 'grass', metsjak 'to jump'

tshj-: tshjar 'mountain sheep'; -tshj-: ratshjan 'I aim (at something)'

sj-: sjaḡ 'I search', sjan 'I kill'; -sj-: tasjet 'hemp'

-swj-: teswje 'tooth', tšhaswje 'the dregs of wine'

zj-: zjaḡ 'I eat'

l̥j-: l̥je 'Buddha; god'

lj-: ljan 'I do it'; -lj-: kalje 'rabbit'

slj-: sljam 'I roll up'

-nj-: ḡanjaḡ 'I am busy', wanjaḡ 'I light; I kindle'

Labials:

pj-: pjak 'pig'; -pj-: kepjar 'jackal'

phj-: phjaḡ 'I divide'

-bj-: kebjar 'leech'

prj-: prje 'fowl'

-mj-: samjaḡ 'I request, ask for'

(a) Velars:

with s/z as first member:

sk-: skaj 'I boil (meat)', skarkhui, 'name of a tree'; -sk-: esku 'its upper side'

skw-: skwam 'to hatch (eggs)'

skj-: skjaɰ 'I boiled (meat)'; -skj-: eskje 'his voice', teskjar 'baked flour'

skh-: skhin 'I gouge out'

-skhj-: laskhje 'a seal'

zg-: zgon 'I want to', zgermu 'moss'; -zg-: tazgular 'a hunchback'

-zgwj-: šazgwje, 'name of a tree'

sɰ-: sɰar 'frost'

With š/z as first member:

šk-: šku 'garlic' škom 'a kind of deer'; -šk-: waški 'to burn', taškai 'scorched'

škr-: škraɰ 'I sift (with a sieve); I am intelligent'; -škr-: teškru 'body', eškrai 'his side'

-škrj-: kaškrje 'to sift (with a sieve)'

škw-: škwaj 'I dig out'

-škh-: teškhur 'sore', peškhai 'just now'

-škhr-: keškfrei 'long'

škhw-: škhwak 'a noise'

zg-: zgeɰ 'I chop down'; -zg-: pazguram 'sausage'

-zgr-: ezgra 'bracelet'; ɰazgro 'fast', ezgra 'its nest'

-zgrj-: ezgrje 'his voice', wezgrje 'the lower level'

-sɰ-: (ke)wašɰom 'fragrant'

With r as first member:

rk-: rkan 'I engrave', rken 'I put in'; -rk-: tarku 'boxing'

-rkj-: tarkje 'mule', merkjau 'you put on; the puts on', kherkje 'dust'

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-rkh-: markhaḡ, n.pr. of a place, skarkhui, name of a tree

-rkhw-: werkhwak 'its husk'

rg-: rgu 'a large rock'; -rg-: terga 'grain'

-rgj-: targje 'dancing and singing', nargjaḡ 'I play'

rḡ-: rḡaḡ 'I borrow'

rḡj-: parḡje 'a wild pig'

With p/b as first member:

pk-: pkuḡ 'I carry on my back', pkaḡ 'I am satiated (with food)'; -pk-:
ṣepkaḡ 'I cover'

-pkj-: wapkje 'its covering', wepkje 'the law of His Majesty'

pkhr-: pkhrat 'to assess', pkhran 'I assess'

With m as first member:

-mk-: temki 'neck', tamkan 'pillow'

-mkr-: tamkra 'crosswise'

mkh-: mkhay 'I am able to do it'; -mkh-: ḡamkhu 'few'

-mchr-: temkhrer 'bile'

mg-: mgeḡ 'I am fed up with, tired of'

-mḡ-: kemḡo 'five', kamḡam 'lying on one's belly'

With ḡ as first member:

-ḡk-: waykai 'to chew'

-ḡkh-: teḡkhu 'behind'

-ḡkhr-: teḡkhru 'charcoal'

ḡg-: ḡgaḡ 'I support, supply'; -ḡg-: keḡgu 'nine', taḡgu 'back'

-ḡgr-: khaṭṣar tṣhiḡgray 'a solution for pickling vegetables'

-ḡwj-: samaḡgwje, n.pr. of a place

(b) Palatals:

With s/z as first member:

stš-: stšak 'eagle', stše 'a tripod which supports a pot', stšipje 'assembly of lamas'; -stš- estšulak 'vomitting', kestše 'previously', tastšu 'writings and paintings'

zdž-: zdži 'wall', zdžim 'cloud'; -zdž-: tazdžam 'cloudy'

With s as first member:

šň-: šňe 'mouth', šňali 'flute'; -šň-: tešňan 'nasal mucus', kešňit 'seven', tešňit 'heart'

With r as first member:

rtš-: rtšim 'I bind'; -rtš-: tartši 'hat', khartšak 'magpie', mertšu 'gray thrush'

-rtšw-: zartšwai, 'n.pr. of a place'

rtšh-: rtšhaɣ 'I peel'

rtšhw-: rtšhwaɣ 'I roll up my sleeves'

rdž-: rdže 'a wild mule'; -rdž-: kherdži 'earthworm', merdžej 'I swallow', kerdžom 'wide'

rž-: ržin 'I plant'; -rž-: perže 'hundred', warže 'eight'

-rň-: tarňi 'gold', tarňan 'mud', tarňek 'hair', kerňak 'deep'

With k as first member:

ktš-: ktšaɣ 'I take out', saktše, 'n.pr. of a place'

-ktšh-: kektšhi 'far'

-kš-: pakšar 'clear'

With m as first member:

-mdž-: temdže 'the lower jaw'

-mš-: temši 'liver'

mň-: mňaɣ 'it is not I', mňatšu 'yoke'; -mň-: temňa 'eye; steamed bread', temње 'field', šamње 'bow', emње 'by the side'

With n as first member:

-ntšw-: tentšwe 'a kind of knife'

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-ndž-: nandžap 'I throw away'

-nž-: smanžo 'a lama's skirt-like garment'

-nǎ-: smanǎingkhui, n.pr. of a place

With ɲ as first member:

-ɲdž-: phaɲdže, name of a 'house', ɬhaɲdže 'a shovel for the fire'

-ɲǎ-: seɲǎap 'I prepare'

(c) Domals:

With ʃ/z as first member:

ʃt-: ʃte 'varnish tree', ʃtaɲ 'I measure', ʃtausje 'a kind of mushroom'

-ʃtj-: teʃtje 'sweat'

ʃtʃ-: ʃtʃi 'ten', ʃtʃeɲ 'I exchange', ʃtʃaɲ 'I see him off'; -ʃtʃ-: keʃtʃi 'wet',
khwaʃtʃan 'silk; satin', kheʃtʃek 'leopard', neʃtʃaɲ 'I ride (horseback)'

ʃtʃh-: ʃtʃheɲ 'I go'

With r as first member:

rtʃ-: rtʃiɲ 'I wash'; -rtʃ-: mertʃi 'flame'

-rtʃh-: tartʃhek 'a little while'

-rtʃ-: serʃa 'fence'

-rz-: tarzek 'wrinkle', warza 'branch'

With k/g as first member:

kt-: kteɲ 'I carry'

ktʃ-: kteɲ 'I crowd (other people)'; -ktʃ-: ʒaktʃan 'stirrup', kektʃin 'near'

-ktʃj-: temoktʃjerei 'uvula'

-ktʃh-: tepaktʃhu 'navel'

kʃ-: kset 'to come', kʃeɲ 'I come'; -kʃ-: tekʃat 'strength', ʃakʃo 'paper'

-gz-: tegz 'sexual organ'

With p as first member:

pt-: ptiɲ 'I walk'; -pt-: ʃapta 'sixteen'

ptʃ-: ptʃalak 'thing, object', ptʃiɣ 'I pay the balance of an account', ptʃaɣ 'I use'; -ptʃ-: tʃiɣptʃu 'a festival in the seventh lunar month'

bdz-: bdzamku 'green'

With m as first member:

mʃ-: mʃeɣ 'it bites me'; -mʃ-: temʃsek 'fire', kemʃser, 'mill'

-mʃh-: temʃhi 'lips'

-mdz-: temdzek 'robbing', memdzeɣ 'I rob'

mʃ-: mʃam 'I worship'; -mʃ-: namʃek 'soul'

With n as first member:

nd-: ndɛɣ 'I chass after (someone)'; -nd-: wandai 'his friend', tandi 'a strip', dandai 'please eat!'

-ntʃ-: tantʃi 'one of a pair'

-ntʃj-: tantʃje 'the shady side of a mountain'

ntʃh-: ntʃhaɣ 'I kill', ntʃhiɣ 'I select'; -ntʃh-: tantʃhi 'pillar', kantʃhai 'market'

-ntʃhj-: kantʃhje 'to kill'

ndz-: ndze 'you (two)'; -ndz-: kandze 'tin'

-nʃ-: dzemkansɪ 'a kind of fruit tree'

With ɣ as first member:

-ɣtʃ-: ʃɛɣtʃan 'a large tree'

-ɣʃ-: raɣʃar 'original'

-ɣz-: ʃɛɣzi 'the ruler of Hell'

-ɣr-: sturo 'a kind of bird'

(d) The dental stops and nasal:

With s/z as first member:

st-: stut 'an image of Buddha', staskui 'a rope connecting yoke and plough',

stalar 'pea', staggak 'a long, embroidered robe worn by lamas'; -st-:

tasto 'an earthen jar', tastai 'bladder', sastu, n.pr. of a place, tshastuɣ 'a

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- stj: mortar for grinding salt'
-stj-: tastje 'saluting to mandarins'
sth-: sthan 'I take out', taso sthide 'one morning'
zd-: zdode 'later on', zdazen 'lunar eclipse', zdaɣaɣ 'a lama's robe'; -zd-:
tazdek 'one section', wezdar 'its fat'
sn-: snɔŋnje 'festivals in the fourth and eighth lunar months', sneimok 'a
kind of mushroom'; -sn-: kasnan 'trousers', wesenaɣwje 'her lover'
-snj-: kesnje 'good', wasnjaɣ 'I make it good'

With ʃ/z as first member:

- ʃt-: ʃtaɣ 'I hide, store away'; -ʃt-: teʃtu 'female sexual organ'
ʃtj-: ʃtjaɣ 'I deposit'; -ʃtj-: uʃtjau 'you store away; he stores away'
ʃth-: ʃthen 'I stretch'; -ʃth-: teʃtha 'girdle'
zd-: zdaɣ 'I am afraid'
zdj-: zdjaɣ 'I am afraid'
-ʃn-: teʃnapa, teʃɳapak 'lips'
ʃnj-: ʃnjaɣ 'I return (something)'

With r as first member:

- rt-: rtam 'I fold', rteɣ 'I am unfortunate'; -rt-: tarta 'hoop', tʃhartan 'pagoda'
-rtj-: zertje, n.pr. of a place, tatartja 'a layer'
-rth-: kasarthom 'to put in order', takurthu 'hair of the head'
rd-: rdaɣ 'I untie', rdeɣ 'I am tired'; -rd-: narduɣ 'I meet', barda 'ringworm'
rdj-: rdjaɣ 'I loosen'; -rdj-: pardjan lamu, n.pr. of a god, terdje 'the process
of thatching a roof'
-rn-: ternom 'brain', tʃsharna 'rain', tarnom 'rib', kerneɳ 'silverfish (the insect)',
ʃarna 'dysentery'
-rnj-: sewurnjaɣ 'I make it red', ternje 'ear'

With k/g as first member:

kt-: ktaj 'I scatter'; -kt-: tektu 'belly; stomach', thaktan 'rent'

gd-: žagdeḡ 'a beam'

With p/b as first member:

pt-: pteḡ 'I hurt (someone)'

-ptj-: šeptjaḡ 'I remember'

pth-: pthaskur 'a head ornament made of coral'; -pth-: wapthis 'near his feet'

With m as first member:

-mt-: temto 'forehead', temte ši, 'name of a tree', emtui 'by the side'

-mtj-: kamemtje 'to talk in one's sleep'

-mth-: temthak 'waist', tamthan 'food: cooked meat and vegetables, but not rice', temthu 'hair of the head', emthe 'profit'

md-: mday 'it stings me', mdamje 'woman', mdak 'fashion, manner'; -md-: temdau 'nephew', temdar 'stinging', temde mu 'widow'

-mdj-: tamdjak 'once', temdje, n.pr. of a place

-mnj-: apamnje, 'name of a house'

With n as first member:

-nt-: kantu 'lying face up', žantan 'knowledge, learning'

-ntj-: ḡantje 'level'

-nth-: šantha 'a lama's shirt', tantha 'one drop'

nd-: ndut 'to have'; -nd-: sandai 'day after tomorrow', kendu, n.pr. of a place, žinda 'host' tsandar 'sandalwood'

nlj-: tsanjje, n.pr. of a place

With ḡ as first member:

-ḡd-: zḡdin 'puttees', tšajdar 'flint and iron for starting a fire'

-ḡdj-: stḡdjan meto, name of a flower

-ḡnj-: snḡnje 'festivals in the fourth and eighth lunar months', kareḡnje 'to hear'

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-ɢl-: tshajɢaj 'a hand bell'

(e) Dental affricates and fricatives:

With r as first member:

rts-: rtsij 'I count'; -rts-: tartsu 'an insane person', kertsu 'the cold season,

-rtsj-: sertsje 'apricot', tertsje 'pulse'

-rtsh-: tertsja 'lungs'

-rs-: tersa 'life'

-rsj-: narsja 'to be ashamed', narsjaɢ 'I am ashamed'

-rz-: tarzek 'a section of a road', skarzaɢ meto, 'name of a flower'

With k/g as first member:

-kts-: tʃhaktso 'locust', tshaktsi 'a kind of bird'

-ktsj-: tektsje 'shoes'

ks-: kseɢ 'I roast'

-gzj-: pagzje 'food for pigs'

With p/b as first member:

-pts-: teptsiu 'marrow', keptsu 'arrow', taptsa 'armpit', taptsiu 'cushions'

ptsj-: ptsjemar 'a kind of bird', ptsjaɢ 'I hold, catch', ptsjeru 'coral beads';

-ptsj-: ʃaptsjaja 'broom', taptsjaja 'braid, queue'

ptsh-: ptshu 'lake, sea', ptshimje 'Hell', ptshin 'I lose money'; eptshi 'excrement',

saptshi 'turban', paptshiʃuʃu 'a kind of bird'

ptshj-: ptshjak 'to kowtow'; -ptshj-: taptshjar 'one sheet (of paper)'

bdz-: bdzaler, n.pr. of a place; -bdz-: tebdzu 'thorns'

-ps-: tʃhapsaɢ 'defecating'

With m as first member:

-mts-: temtso 'lunch', ramtsu 'button'

-mtsh-: wamtsher 'lying on one's side'

-mtshj-: kemtshjar 'beautiful'

-mdz-: kamdzo 'to fast', samdzen 'close your mouth!'

-ms-: kawamso 'wedge', tšamso 'a musk deer'

-msj-: zamsje 'saluting lamas'

With n as first member:

-nts-: rantsiɣ 'I cut'

-ntsh-: nentshoɣ 'I lick'

-ntshj-: nentshjoɣ 'I lick', wantshjaɣ 'a cupboard for kitchen utensils'

-ndz-: tandzi 'a long, protruding tooth', tandza 'a little bit', kasatsenzak 'to connect'

With ɣ as first member:

-ɣts-: tateɣtsi 'one ch'ién (a unit of weight)'

-ɣs-: sajsi 'breath'

-ɣz-: tšujzo 'stone stairs'

(f) Labials:

With s/z as first member:

sp-: spat 'incense', span 'glue', sper 'shrub', spu 'roof', spemje, 'name of a tree'; -sp-: khaspa 'basket', taspu 'pus', waspar 'his capital', waspai 'underneath'

-spj-: džaspje 'much; many'

-zb-: tazbo 'brothers', wazbo 'its nest'

sm-: smanžo 'a lama's skirt-like garment', smanñiɣkhui, n.pr. of a place, smak 'wool', sman 'medicine', smerer 'a wild willow tree'; -sm-: ɣasmi 'ripe, cooked'

With ʂ/z as first member:

ʂp-: ʂpaɣ 'I know how to do it', ʂpen 'I feed'; -ʂp-: kheʂpet 'domestic animals'

-ʂpr-: užʂpret 'to change, become'

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ʃpj-: ʃpjaɣ 'I am thirsty'; -ʃpj-: khaʃpje 'a kind of frog', deʃpjaɣ 'I am thirsty'

zb-: khazbalulu 'butterfly'

-zbr-: tazbrok 'kicking'

-zbj-: tezbe 'chin'

ʃm-: ʃmoɣ 'I mix and knead the dough'; -ʃm-: raʃmiɣ 'I talk', teʃmi 'tongue'

With r as first member:

-rp-: tarpi 'chanting prayers', tarpom 'ice', terpet 'seed'

-rpj-: ʃarpje 'a kind of axe', taterpjet 'one catty', tarpjak 'shoulder', marpjaɣ 'I carry on my shoulder'

-rph-: terphu 'a fir tree', tekharpha 'cheek'

-rb-: lerbu 'jewel, precious object', terbo 'drum'

rm-: rmaɣ 'I sleep'; -rm-: termi 'man', tarmo 'dragon', termu 'hail', smermu 'specter', kharmu 'leather bellows'

-rmj-: karmje 'to sleep'

With k/g as first member:

-kp-: lakpat 'sleeve'

-kpr-: tekprei 'message'

-kprj-: ŋakprje 'meat dumpling'

-kpj-: tephakpjet 'thigh'

-kph-: takphu 'a flock', ʃakphu 'tree'

With m as first member:

-mp-: wempu 'outside'

mph-: mphaɣ 'I buy', mphoɣ 'I wrap'; -mph-: temphas 'vomitting'

mphrj-: mphrjen 'I repair'

mphj-: mphjaɣ 'I sell'; -mphj-: memphjaɣ 'I vomit'

-mb-: wembu 'his body'

-mbr-: tembra 'weeding', šambra 'a small spade'

-mbrj-: tšhimbrje 'temple'

-mbj-: tambje, n.pr. of a place

With n as first member:

-nb-: lenbu 'tribal chief', denbu 'going out'

-nbj-: lenbu karatanbje, 'a personal name'

With ɣ as first member:

-ɣp-: šɣpu 'calabash'

-ɣpj-: luɣpje 'place; valley', tuɣpje 'apron'

-ɣph-: kaɣphu, n.pr. of a place

-ɣb-: laɣbuʈʂhi 'elephant'

-ɣm-: tuɣmar 'a long trumpet', maɣmi 'soldier'

-ɣmj-: kuɣmje 'emperor'

7.

-i-: khi 'dog', tši 'wheat; excrement', zdži 'wall'

-iu-: tažiu 'face'

-is-: wapthis 'near his feet'

-ir-: tažir 'shadow; soul'

-ip-: kartšip 'to bind, wind'

-im-: zdžim 'cloud'

-it-: waržit 'his shadow'

-in-: zaɣdin 'puttees'

-ik-: karantsik 'to cut'

-iɣ-: tsiɣ 'I say'

-e-: kwje 'kitchen', khre 'rice', khwje 'bedroom', stše 'a tripod which supports a pot', tše 'wine', rdže 'a wild mule'

-ei-: khorei 'snake', nardžei 'we/you/they run'

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- eu: keu 'you buy; he buys'
- es: kapes 'tinder'
- er: ser 'drill, awl', sper 'shrub', nardžer 'we two/you two/they two run'
- ep: tep 'to sew', tekjep 'needle'
- em: tem 'I sew'
- et: terpet 'seed', tatarpjet 'one catty'
- en: slapen 'teacher', natjen 'to be placed somewhere', kapen 'you come here'
- ek: komtek 'bolt (of a door)', kanardžek 'to run'
- eɣ: kheɣ 'tiger', breɣ 'rhinoceros', nardžeɣ 'I run'
- a: kwa 'spade', zgra 'bracelet', ptshja 'kneeling', tersa 'life'
- ai: swai 'barley', zai 'ladder'
- au: temdau 'nephew'
- as: pas 'a wild animal similar to a pig', khepas 'a food fly'
- ar: khjar 'steelyard', sjar 'frost', tshjar 'mountain sheep', sar 'louse', wezdar 'its fat'
- ap: tap 'to beat'
- am: kam 'the colter of a plough', tšham 'a lama's dance'
- at: spat 'incense'
- an: span 'glue', brestan 'a cushion by the fireplace'
- ak: stšak 'eagle', prak 'rock', smak 'wool'
- aɣ: meŋaɣ 'cat', paɣ 'I do'
- o: tewo 'a pond where buffalos drink'
- oi: namoi 'your throat'
- or: kapkor 'to carry on one's back'
- om: škom 'a kind of deer', šom 'iron', kom 'door', žom 'pot, pan'
- ot: bot 'Tibet'
- on: nažon 'to wait for you'

- ok: kaʂok 'to cut'
- oŋ pkɔŋ 'I carry on my back'
- u: ʂku 'garlic', rgu 'a large rock', tʂu 'stone', dʒu 'bamboo', tshu 'stove',
ptshu 'lake; sea', spu 'roof'
- ui: khui 'bowl'
- us: wakus 'on his head'
- ur: kapkur 'to carry on one's back'
- up: tup 'to beat'
- um: tum 'I beat'
- ut' stut 'an image of Buddha', dut n.pr. of a cruel man (in legends), ndut
'to have'
- un: rkun 'I put in'
- uŋ: pkuŋ 'I carry on my back'